

Collection policy for SND CARE

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Swedish National Data Service

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Background

Swedish National Data Service (SND) is a Swedish national infrastructure for research data funded by the Swedish Research Council.

According to the agreement with the Swedish Research Council the purpose of the infrastructure is:

To facilitate sharing of research data in a simple, secure, and reliable manner, while complying with the requirements of preservation, access, and sharing;

To make data visible and provide user statistics by showcasing research data nationally and internationally, and providing information about how the data are shared and cited;

To facilitate reliable access to findable, high-quality, and well-documented research data, along with information about how these data can be accessed and reused.

SND is a certified repository (CoreTrustSeal).¹ The certified part of the operations at SND is called SND CARE and includes the data stored at SND.

This document describes the principles for which research data can be deposited at SND CARE. Research data refers to digital material that can form the basis for scientific analysis regardless of the research field.

Scope

WHY of data deposited in SND CARE :

- research;
- replication and validation;
- education and training.

WHAT can be deposited in SND CARE:

- data of interest for research;
- data that are documented in a way that they can be understood and reused now and in the future;
- data that do not contain information that it would be unlawful to disseminate and grant access to, or whose access does not violate existing agreements;
- data that contain personal information can only be deposited in SND CARE if there is a data processing agreement between SND and the research principal unless the research principal is the University of Gothenburg.

¹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

HOW are data deposited in SND CARE:

- data and documentation files are deposited in the SND documentation system DORIS by uploading a copy of the files;
- large datafiles are deposited through an sftp server;
- SND CARE reserves the right to refuse data under the following conditions:
 - data do not meet the criteria outlined in SND's Collection Policy;
 - data cannot be described in a manner that fulfils SND's requirements and recommendations for data and metadata;²
 - preconditions for data reuse and accessibility cannot be agreed upon;
 - data and related materials are of such nature or volume that processing them is difficult or impossible given the resources and capacity at SND CARE.

Related documents and policies

Requirements and recommendations for data and metadata in SND's research data catalogue (2021, in Swedish). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6351364>

Preservation and management of research data at the Swedish National Data Service (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6477109>

SND Policy for Persistent Identifiers (PID) on Research Data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6477023>

SND Policy for Review of Data and Metadata (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6477041>

² Requirements and recommendations for data and metadata in SND's research data catalogue (2021). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6351364> (only in Swedish)